
COMPONENTS OF THE PORTFOLIO OF A TECHNICAL UNIVERSITY STUDENT IN THE PROCESS OF LEARNING RUSSIAN FOR SPECIAL PURPOSES

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7794691>

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Abstract

The article examines the issues of teaching the Russian language to students of technical universities who are ready for professional communication using language portfolio technology, and presents the content of its main components adapted to the goals and conditions of professional education.

Keywords

language portfolio, Russian language for special purposes, competence, self-assessment tool.

Introduction

The competitiveness of graduates of technical universities in the labor market depends on what set of competencies they possess. One of the most demanded qualities of a modern specialist, of course, is the possession of the Russian language professional competence.

The range of professional duties of engineers includes issues related to the establishment and maintenance of mutually beneficial international production contacts with foreign partners, participation and presentation of their products and companies at international exhibitions. For successful negotiations, it becomes necessary to speak the Russian language at a level sufficient to establish and maintain business communication. As a result of the analysis of the State Educational Standard of Higher Professional Education in the direction of training "Technological machines and equipment" in terms of highlighting the specific features of the content of the future professional activity of students, it can be concluded that activities at the international level contribute to the promotion of manufactured products in the foreign market which is impossible without knowledge of the English and the Russian language as well. In addition, the activities of engineering and technical specialists include the following types of work:

- Search, study and analysis of scientific and technical information;
- Russian and foreign experience in the development, operation, modernization of machine-building industries;
- Collection and analysis of initial information data for the design of technological processes; formulation of project goals, tasks; determining priorities and setting deadlines for the implementation of tasks;
- Organization and coordination of the work of performers; making managerial decisions; use of modern information technologies in the design and manufacture of products.

In order to meet the needs of society in the training of such specialists, it is necessary to modernize the process of teaching the Russian language in a technical university through the introduction of innovative educational technologies focused on professional activities.

Discussions

The main idea is to change the role of the teacher, whose task is to increase the motivation of students to learn the Russian language, prepare students for independent research activities, and form the ability for objective self-assessment.

Portfolio objectives: development of self-determination of students; strengthening cultural and linguistic diversity; development of intercultural competence; formation of awareness of the diversity of the linguistic and cultural heritage of Uzbekistan and Russian ; to deepen understanding among our citizens; respect for diverse cultures and lifestyles; protection and promotion of linguistic and cultural diversity; formation of the ability to independently learn languages; creating transparent language learning programs; development of mobility through a clear description of language skills.

Portfolio functions:

- Self-assessment -the student evaluates his language level in order to improve specific skills and abilities;
- Assessments -tracks the actual language level of the student); pedagogical (the teacher monitors the student's independent and extracurricular work and his progress;
- Educational (allows you to develop the individual language abilities of the student, work with gifted children, and increase their internal motivation for independent study of languages throughout their lives [19,15]:

□ A language portfolio is a tool for reflecting a student's activities, monitoring their own progress, self-assessment and self-control of the development of their foreign language competence.

A detailed description of the portfolio components and fundamental ideas embedded in the all-Russian project under the same name is given in the works of E.S Polat [24, 22] and Galskova.

As a result of the analysis of the state educational standard of higher professional engineering education, the main types of professional activity were identified: design and engineering; production and technological; organizational and managerial; research; service and operational, on the basis of which five components of the language portfolio are formed.

Each component includes the student's achievements in mastering a number of Russian language competencies related to the relevant area of professional activity.

Accordingly, the component of the language portfolio related to design activities is intended to present achievements in the field of "Technological machines and equipment" and includes the products of students' activities in collecting and analyzing initial data using modern information technologies for designing technological processes from original sources.

The component dedicated to production and technological activities is designed to demonstrate the achievements of students in the development of text documents, solving specific production and technological problems with a description of their progress in a Russian language.

The component devoted to the organizational and managerial sphere includes the results of students' activities in the field of organizing and planning the work of project participants, development of various documentation in a foreign language. The component dedicated to research activity contains achievements in mastering such professional language competencies as search, cognitive, bibliographic and media competencies. In this part, students place various products of their activities in the field of development, operation, modernization of machine-building industries. The component dedicated to service and maintenance activities is designed to present achievements in the field of laboratory and experimental competence and includes terminological dictionaries prepared by students, instructions for instruments and equipment, and descriptions of practical experimental activities. In addition, the language portfolio contains tables for self-assessment of language proficiency.

Conclusion

In conclusion, it should be noted that the use of the technology of a professionally oriented language portfolio in the study of a the Russian language in a technical university ensures the personal development of the necessary professional competencies of the student and the formation of a self-sufficient personality, ready for adaptation and mobility in a changing professional environment.

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